

Nursery age, field duration, and grain yield of rice

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We studied the effect of nursery age on the time of 50% flowering, maturity, and grain yield of rice. Seedlings aged 25, 30, 35, 40, and 45 d were transplanted on the same day in 1983-84 wet and dry seasons. In wet season, TKM9, a 105-d variety, was sown in Jun. In dry season, AD9408, a 125-d variety, was sown in Oct. NPK at 75-17-31 kg/ha was applied in wet season and 100-22-42 in dry season.

Effect of seedling age on 2 rice characteristics and yield, Aduthurai, India.

Seedling age (d)	Wet season			Dry season		
	Time to 50% flowering (d)	Time to maturity (d)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Time to 50% flowering (d)	Time to maturity (d)	Grain yield (t/ha)
25	51	82	6.0	64	95	4.3
30	48	81	5.9	62	94	4.2
35	45	79	5.7	61	93	4.2
40	43	77	5.7	57	92	4.0
45	42	77	5.2	57	92	4.0
CD (P = 0.05)	2	1	0.4	2	2	0.5

A 20-d difference in nursery age (25- to 45-d-old seedlings) produced a difference of 8 d in 50% flowering in wet season and 6 d in dry season. The difference in maturity was 4 d for both seasons (see table). It took less time (30 d) for seedlings planted at 25 d to go from 50%

flowering to maturity than for those planted at 45 d (35 d).

Planting older seedlings reduced wet season yield, but did not affect yield in dry season. □

Evaluation of conventional, slow-release, and nitrification-inhibitor-treated fertilizers for rice in an alkali soil

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In India, crop growth is reduced on 2.5 million ha of alkali (sodic) soils that have excess exchangeable sodium, high pH, and poor hydraulic conductivity. To increase productivity, farmers apply gypsum or iron pyrites, after which rice is grown as the first crop because it tol-

erates soil alkalinity. Proper N management during and after reclamation is important.

We evaluated conventional, slow-release, and nitrification-inhibitor-treated fertilizers in a pot experiment in 1981 wet season. Ceramic pots were filled with 6 kg of surface soil from a barren alkali patch (sandy loam, Calciorthid aquic Natrustalf, pH 10.5, EC₂ 0.57 mmho/cm, 12.1 meq cation exchange capacity/100 g, 3.02% CaCO₃, 0.12% organic carbon, 0.038% total N, 40 kg available N/ha, 40 ppm Olsen's P, and 332 kg available K/ha).

Twenty-five percent of the required gypsum was surface-mixed, then leached for 28 d. Final in situ pH was 9.5. Forty five-d-old seedlings were transplanted after 12.5 ppm ZnSO₄ was mixed in the surface 5 cm and the pots were flooded with 2.5 cm water. Each pot had 4 hills with 2 Pusa 2-21 plants/hill, in 5 replications.

After 4 d, when only a film of water remained on the surface, N fertilizer (60 ppm N) was broadcast and incorporated in the surface 5 cm soil. The pots were immediately flooded to 5 cm depth, and

Effect of conventional, slow-release, and nitrification-inhibitor-treated fertilizers on rice yield and N uptake in an alkali soil, Haryana, India.^a

Treatment	25 DT			45 DT			Maturity			
	DM (g)	N uptake (mg)	N uptake efficiency ^b (%)	DM (g)	N uptake (mg)	N uptake efficiency ^b (%)	Straw (g)	Grain (g)	N uptake (mg)	N uptake efficiency ^b (%)
No N	3.2	32.1	—	3.4	35.5	—	4.0	1.3	41.9	—
Urea	6.1	138.2	29.5	15.0	131.1	26.6	14.5	9.4	176.0	37.2
Urea ^c	4.1	57.7	21.3	9.5	101.7	27.6	16.4	12.1	245.5	56.5
Ammonium sulfate	5.2	141.2	30.3	11.3	139.2	28.8	17.4	11.8	218.7	49.2
Ammonium sulfate ^c	3.2	71.7	33.0	11.3	125.8	37.6	14.1	11.7	211.3	47.0
Sulfur-coated urea	3.4	73.3	11.5	8.4	92.9	16.0	9.8	8.6	179.8	38.3
Neem cake-blended urea	4.5	101.4	19.3	17.7	159.8	34.5	14.5	14.0	217.7	48.8
Coal tar extract-treated urea	6.0	121.8	24.9	16.8	159.8	34.5	14.7	11.1	179.5	38.2
N-serve treated urea	5.0	121.1	24.7	11.8	125.5	25.0	14.1	9.7	166.9	34.7
LSD (P = 0.05)							4.8	5.5		

^aDT = d after transplanting, DM = dry matter. ^bApparent N uptake efficiency = $\frac{\text{N uptake in treatment} - \text{N uptake in control}}{\text{N applied}} \times 100$. ^cSplit application.